

The consequences of the perceived organizational justice: a holistic overview

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Abstract:

Organizational justice gained a burgeoning interest in academic and corporate areas, it is a virtue of social organizations. In the working environment, individuals react depending on their perceptions. Therefore, perceived organizational justice is a behavioral concept that refers to the subjective description of the fairness of remuneration, decision-making processes and relationships within the organization. These justice perceptions have been empirically related to positive and negative consequences on attitudes, behaviors, and health such as greater identification and commitment, better organizational trust, increased job satisfaction, reinforced job performance, promoted employees' organizational citizenship behavior, improved health and wellbeing as well as counterproductive behaviors. Despite the vigor of fairness research, the rapid flourishing of this literature has made relevant a variety of new issues. Hence, drawing upon equity theory and social exchange theory, this theoretical paper is designed to investigate the prominent literature in order to develop a holistic overview portraying the individual level of the perceived organizational justice and point out its salient consequences, based on recent theoretical and empirical research.

It is anticipated that this paper will have a significant contribution to the advancement of organizational justice research literature and provide managers and scholars to get a better insight into harmonizing the relationship between employee and employers. Since, organizational justice has the potential to produce powerful benefits for organizations and employees alike.

In the present paper, we discuss the main definitions and dimensions of organizational justice in accordance with the descriptive and subjective approach, in addition, we present the principal outcomes of fairness and unfairness treatments.

Keywords: Organizational justice, fairness judgments, positive outcomes, negative outcomes.

JEL Classification: L20

Paper type: Theoretical Research

1. Introduction

Currently, the increased globalization and the intensified competition have engulfed the world. This challenging global crisis has forced many organizations in both developed and developing economies to survive and to be able to cope with. Consequently, it has amplified pressures on the organizations and has brought about many organizational changes (e.g. new working patterns, workforce reconfiguration...), severely affecting Human Resources that are the key factor of maintaining existence, effectiveness and success of organizations.

Therefore, in order to adjust these changes and to jointly overcome (the firm and its employees) the effects of this crisis, justice in this era has a vital role to play in organizations, as it is at the pinnacle of organizational values (Rawls, 1971), it concerns both the organization and the employees to develop a reciprocal social relationship (Blau, 1964; Organ, 1988) and cooperation actions (Barnard, 1938) to support orientations of organizational management decisions (Swalhi et al., 2017). In other words, the organization is a structured social system, its perennity and balance are highly related to the presence of strong bonds between its constituent elements, Hence justice holds employees and the organization together, “*whereas injustice can pull them apart*” (Folger & Cropanzano, 1998, p. 12).

Furthermore, the justice construct was adapted to organizations and evolved as an essential aspect of organizational behavior over the past few decades (e.g. Adams 1965; Blau 1964; Homans 1961; Leventhal 1976; Walker and Thibaut 1970), it gained a broader and keen interest in both academic and corporate arenas. One of the starting points, theories of justice have emerged for the development of human societies and have been borrowed from old traditional, philosophical and religious ideologies. Considering it as a fundamental concept in the philosophical field, it has been defended as a normative and prescriptive approach, whereas in the management field, organizational justice is defined as a personal perception and evaluation of what is just or unjust in the workplace (Russell Cropanzano et al., 2007). Justice is closely associated with equity and fairness, Adam’s equity theory (1963, 1965) was designed firstly to interpret justice in organizations based on the individual's perception of equity distribution of allocations and outcomes. On the other hand, theorists began to generalize the concept of justice, for instance, Greenberg (1987), the coiner of organizational justice, defined it as how the employees perceive the behaviors and the decisions of the organization, and how those impacts the collaborators’ attitudes at work.

Indeed, employees are daily confronted with decisions that they are described as "fair" or "unfair" based on personal judgments and subjective criteria. Their perception of justice is essential to take into account since it will lead to attitudes and actions within the company: a sense of justice will promote attachment to the company, trust in managers, acceptance of decisions, job satisfaction and will increase the appearance of positive behaviors, such as mutual aid, courtesy, performance, etc. On the other hand, a feeling of unfairness perceived by the employee will have notorious effects such as low acceptance of changes, higher absenteeism, turnover and even theft.

For this, the aim of this work is to examine the prominent literature to develop a portray of a holistic overview of the individual level of perceived organizational justice, drawing upon equity theory and social exchange theory, and point out its salient consequences in reference to recent theoretical and empirical research.

To carry out our analysis, this paper is organized into the following sections. It begins firstly by introducing the methodology used to scrutinize the literature on the perceived organizational justice. Secondly, it defines the organizational justice concept and presents its dimensions. Thirdly, it sheds a considerable light on a landscape of its significant impacts. Finally, it proposes concluding thoughts for future research.

2. Research Methodology

Scientific research aims to solve problems relating to a specific field. Organizational issues are analyzed in an attempt to enhance scientific knowledge and support managers to improve a better understanding of a phenomenon and then make the appropriate managerial decisions.

This theoretical paper presents a holistic view of the organizational justice field at the individual level perception, it synthesizes the gist of the literature review.

In practical terms, various keywords were utilized such as perceived organizational justice, fairness, organizational justice dimensions, equity theory, social exchange theory, organizational justice outcomes, consequences of perceived organizational justice, organizational justice impacts, influence of organizational justice, organizational justice effects. Based on different Library databases (e.g. Scopus, Jstor, Springer, Sciences Direct, APA Psycnet and Frontiers in psychology). The keyword searching process has oriented the research to a plethora of empirical and theoretical studies (e.g. Colquitt et al., 2013; Crawshaw et al., 2013; Russell Cropanzano et al., 2001, 2007; Russell Cropanzano & Rupp, 2003; Greenberg, 1987, 2008) and to a noteworthy meta-analytic studies (e.g. Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt et al., 2001; Viswesvaran & Ones, 2002), including the most relevant scientific journals (e.g. International Journal of Human Resource Management, Academy of Management Journal, Journal of Management Development, Journal of Applied Psychology, Journal of Business Ethics). Thereby, the most important studies in the field of organizational justice would be better exposed and analyzed.

3. Perceived organizational justice

3.1 Perceived organizational justice: Descriptive and subjective approaches

Philosophical scientists like Plato and Aristotle, underlined that organizational justice adopts a prescriptive and normative approaches, which lead to determine actions that are truly just, it refers to how employees should behave in the workplace (El Akremi et al., 2006) using logic and observation (Cugueró-Escofet & Fortin, 2014). Otherwise, for these scholars, the organizational justice sets norms and standards that should be respected in the workplace. However, management researchers argued that the organizational justice is framed by a descriptive approach, i.e., we are interested in how people act, by describing the likely results of a particular employee situation (Crawshaw et al., 2013; Russell Cropanzano et al., 2007; El Akremi et al., 2006) they seek to understand behavioral and attitudinal employees' reactions toward a fair or unfair event. In addition, organizational justice approach is subjective, it focuses on what individuals subjectively consider and think is right or fair instead of an objective reality (Russell Cropanzano et al., 2007). By contrast, several authors have criticized this approach, showing that it does not necessarily lead to ethical decision-making, because what individuals report does not essentially represent either reality or what needs to be done (El Akremi et al., 2006).

Cropanzano and his colleagues (2001) pointed out the philosophical roots of the descriptive approach, which leads to its complementarity with the normative and prescriptive approach. Organizational justice researchers borrow philosophical concepts to study them descriptively (Russell Cropanzano & Molina, 2015), more specifically, they tend to examine how people react when standards of justice are respectfully settled or violated (Crawshaw et al., 2013).

In that sense, Colquitt et al., (2001) demonstrated that between 1975 and 2000, there were 183 studies highlighted the importance of fairness in organizations, and Greenberg (1987) was the first author that invented the organizational justice concept and he closely associated it with fairness, referring to the equity theory (Adams, 1965; Homans, 1961) (it will be detailed more in the section below), he denoted that the notion of organizational justice is a personal evaluation and perception of the fairness of resource allocation in organizations, it means,

expressing how employees perceive the behaviors and the decisions of organizations, and how those impact the employees' attitude at work.

Furthermore, for Moorman (1991) and James (1993), organizational justice describes individuals' perceptions and reactions toward fair or unfair treatment within an organization, it reflects an individual's intuition of justice in an organization. Besides Folger and Cropanzano (1998) defined Organizational justice as the rules that are put in place to allocate or make decisions about the allocation of acquisitions, and the societal norms that form the basis of these rules for regulating people's relations. According to Beugré and Baron (2001, p. 326) organizational justice is *"a perceptual and practical social system that contains individual's perception of his/her relationship with collaborators, superordinates, and institution"*. With other terms, organizational justice pertains to a social system that governs the perception of individuals' relationships with each other, with their superiors and with their organization. Cropanzano et al (2001) attempted to define organizational justice as the individual's perceptions of behavioral reactions and how these perceptions affect the results of the organization.

As it can be seen, several authors have endeavored to define the concept of organizational justice from a different perspective over the years, focusing on the different facets of justice (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2002) which confirm its plurality, as a matter of fact, it is suggested to opt for the definition of (Beugre, 1998), which seems to be general and includes all the dimensions of this notion, it emphasizes that organizational justice is a social system that describes the perception of fairness within social and economic exchanges taking place in the organization, involving the individual in his relations with superiors, subordinates, colleagues, and the organization. Otherwise, organizational justice is the perceived fairness of organizational outcomes, processes, and interpersonal relationships (Cropanzano & Greenberg, 1997).

3.2 The components of Organizational Justice:

The literature states that organizational justice can take various forms, generally, three types can be distinguished (Colquitt, 2001; Greenberg, 1990). In the chronological progress of justice theories, it is notable that distributive justice has emerged firstly, then respectively came procedural justice and interactional justice:

- Distributive justice: represents the collection and evaluation of rewards and resource allocations within an organization.
- Procedural justice: refers to the perception of the decision-making process.
- Interactional justice (which includes interpersonal and informational justice): is the perception of interpersonal behavior.

Overall justice is an emerging dimension that encompasses all of these components of organizational justice in one dimension, it refers to a global perception of fairness based on personal experiences as well as on the experiences of others (Ambrose & Schminke, 2009).

3.2.1 Distributive Justice:

The theory of relative deprivation and cognitive dissonance theory are the origin of distributive justice (Frimousse et al., 2008). Through this theory, Stouffer and his colleague (1949) showed that the sense of injustice and dissatisfaction triggered by American airmen is not the result of absolute deprivation, but rather of the comparison of the working conditions of one person with those of another. It is therefore a divergence between what has been perceived and what should be a right, as (Spector, 1956) and (Thibaut, 1950) have made clear in their experimental work, this feeling is a response to a gap between an achievement and the expectation of that achievement (Adams, 1965). Concerning the theory of cognitive dissonance

previously called the theory of consistency (Festinger, 1957), Festinger argued that the contradiction of beliefs, values, opinions, and knowledge creates a psychological state of discomfort that induces a feeling of injustice.

Based on these two theories (Adams, 1965; Homans, 1961) invented the theory of equity, it is noteworthy that it has taken up an enormous amount of space in the literature review of organizational justice, and is characterized by 3 phases (Peretti, 2004):

- **Exchange evaluation:** This phase consists of evaluating all the contributions or so-called inputs or investments (e.g. Experience, education, training, effort, knowledge, capacities, seniority...) and outcomes (e.g. rewards, wages, social approval, job security, career opportunities, remuneration, promotion).
- **Comparison:** Comparing the ratio of an individual's contributions (inputs: I) and rewards (Outcomes: O) either with a colleague who considers himself as a referent, with his initial state, or with an imaginary referent. $\frac{O_X}{I_X} = \frac{O_Y}{I_Y}$
- **Action:** According to Adams, people pay attention to over-reward, as well as under the reward, when there is a result of non-equity (Over-equity or under-equity), the individual begins to act with the aim of finding the balance to restore equity depending on circumstances.

Moreover, Deutsch (1975) postulated that there are three essential rules of distributive justice:

- **Equity:** rewarding employees according to their contributions. For example, if an employee observes that his or her ratio is upper or lower than that of a referent person, automatically, he or she will attempt to modify it depending on circumstances, by either raising performance or lowering performance. Generally, equity allocations are used with the objective to maximize productivity.
- **Equality:** offering each employee approximately the same pay, without regard to contributions. The aim of equality allocations is to create harmony in the workplace.
- **The need:** guaranteeing compensation according to the personal needs necessary of each one.

3.2.2 Procedural justice:

Procedural justice can be considered as the decency of operations, procedures and techniques that are utilized to achieve the final decision (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). Thibaut and Walker were the pioneers of procedural justice in the 1970's. They defined their theory as the employees' subjective perception of how the compensation system and all policies and procedures are developed, and how they are executed collectively and individually. In other words, it refers to employees' judgments of fairness of all organizational policies, management and procedures leading to taking decisions (Colquitt, 2001). Since individuals are sensitive to the procedures applied by decision-makers to distribute retribution and make decisions (Colquitt et al., 2005). For instance, Employees perceive at the workplace several procedural issues such as reward systems, internal promotion, employment opportunities...

Thibaut and Walker (1970) subdivided procedural justice into two phases : the process control, and the decision control, the first one means the ability to voice one's views and arguments during a procedure, i.e., procedural justice is achieved when employees feel they can intervene to express their opinion regarding the decision-making process, while the second one is the ability to influence the actual outcome itself.

By contrast, Leventhal (1976; 1980) argued that "voice" is only one of the main determinants of procedural justice, then, he added a list of attributes of procedural justice as follows:

- **Free from bias:** Decision-making processes must not be affected by self-interest or be based on existing preconceptions.

- Ethical: Procedures must follow ethical standards and moral values, for example: lack of corruption, disappointment, theft of resources...
- Accuracy: Procedures should be based on the most truthful, valid and correct information.
- Consistency: Procedures must be coherent and consistent over time and between people, it means guaranteeing similar treatment across all individuals and times.
- Representativeness: Procedures must ensure that all individuals and all parties affected by the decision, have the opportunity to interact, express their opinions and preoccupations based on their values and perspectives.
- Correction: Procedures should be flexible for modification or reversal of decisions in case of mistakes.

3.2.3 Interactional Justice:

Certain studies characterized the interactional justice as the social aspect of procedural justice (Tyler & Bies, 1990), this third component of organizational justice is considered to be the simplest one, since it refers to the way individuals are treated within the organization. In other terms, when it comes to setting up the organizational procedures, employees perceive the fairness of their hierarchical supervisor, quality in social relations, communication and transparency (Bies, 2001; Bies & Moag, 1986). It is subdivided into two main components: interpersonal justice, which refers to the dignified and respectful treatment of individuals, and informational justice, which represents the proper sharing and explanation of information and data Colquitt (2001). Furthermore, Bies & Moag (1986) identified four criteria for interactional justice which are: justification, truthfulness, respect, and propriety.

Broadly, in a historical and chronological sense, distributive justice wave extended from the 1950s to the 1970s, the wave of procedural justice stretched from the end of the 1970s to 1990s, in 1990's begun the interactional justice wave (Colquitt et al., 2005). Researchers sought to study the combination of organizational justice dimensions in order to evaluate their interactional and dichotomy link (e.g. Brockner 2002; Cropanzano and Schminke 2001).

3.2.4 Overall Justice

Previously, justice theory emphasized that individuals make perceptions of each type of justice (Colquitt, 2001). However, this fragmentation of organizational justice structure has presented some limits. In practical terms, work conditions, the high demands of the typical workplace and the lack of necessary cognitive resources complicate the evaluation of fairness dimensions separately (Ambrose & Schminke, 2009; Nicklin et al., 2014). Consequently, the global justice concept has emerged recently, starting at the beginning of the 21st century, namely overall justice. For Cropanzano and Molina (2015, p. 382) overall justice is that *"individuals form global judgments of how they are treated. Instead of focusing on the different sets of justice perceptions as three (or four) pieces of a puzzle"*. Otherwise, in real organizational life, employees do not care about a particular type of justice, they evaluate and react towards an experience or situation depending on their own global vision.

Nevertheless, the concept of overall justice is not opposed to the fairness dimensions, in cognitive terms, when individuals express a global opinion, they have indirectly passed through particular perceptions of justice in a *"bottom-up"* manner (Russell Cropanzano & Molina, 2015).

Throughout the literature, it is proven empirically that organizational justice with all these components leads to major consequences which will be analyzed below.

4. Consequences of OJ:

The outcomes of organizational justice presented below were selected in accordance with what is commonly examined in the literature, as well as for their pivotal role in improving the understanding of organizational justice perceptions and enhancing organizational effectiveness and performance.

Indeed, analyzing and understanding the individual level of perceived justice and injustice impacts in the workplace enables researchers and managers to predict positive and negative reactions that could occur in the workplace. Thus, many researches have been conducted in different organizational contexts and have shown that organizational justice affects workers' attitudes, behaviors, emotions, performance, and health, and can cause deviant behaviors. In this section, we will overview the principal consequences of individuals when they feel they are treated fairly or not.

4.1 Organizational Commitment:

Commitment is a key success factor for the company's survival. Employees become extremely committed when they feel the strength of the bond towards their firm (Steers, 1977) cited by (Imamoglu et al., 2019), it indicates their intention to stay or to leave the organization. Organizational commitment allows employees to proceed to work in the organization, to participate efficiently, to make an extra effort with added value and creativity and to become loyal to the organization.

Several researchers have revealed that organizational justice is a predictor of commitment (e.g. Rahman, et al., 2016; Karem et al., 2019) and all organizational components play a substantial role in organizational commitment. They have acknowledged that when employees perceive that the retribution is equally distributed regarding their contributions, they express a high attachment towards the organization. In addition, when employees feel that they are on an equal footing with others in terms of decision-making and processes, and their superiors treat them equally, they belong and get involved into the organization. Consequently, they embrace the objectives of the organization, because they see themselves as an important part of the organization (Imamoglu et al., 2019).

By contrast, injustice in organization leads to the lack of commitment which may cause counterproductive behaviors (they will be detailed in the last section below), like high rates of absenteeism and turnover intention, and decreased performance which negatively affects organization efficiency and effectiveness (Becker & Barry, 1996) cited by (Karem et al., 2019).

4.2 Organizational Identification:

Stemming from the social identity theory (Ashforth & Mael, 1989) and the self-categorization theory (Turner, 1985) organizational identification refers to "*the perceived oneness with an organization and the experience of the organization's success or failures as one's own*" (Mael & Asiforth, 1992, p. 103). It is "*the perception of oneness with or belongingness to*" (Ashforth & Mael, 1989, p. 34), this psychological attachment, self-reference and the sense of belonging to the organization, makes employees see themselves as part of the organization and contributing to the organization's success (Twenge et al., 2007). In fact, they relate to the objectives, values and tasks of their organization (Malhotra et al., 2020) they become integrated with the aims of the organization (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). In turn employees feel a sense of respect, pride and esteem towards the firm.

Few previous studies have conducted the association between organizational identification and organizational justice (Malhotra et al., 2020) despite their important link. When employees feel that they are fairly treated, incomes are justly distributed, decisions are well made taking into account their voice, they systematically identify themselves with the organization.

4.3 Job Satisfaction:

Robbins and his teammates (2008) indicated that job satisfaction is when employees prove a positive feeling about one's work as a consequence of the evaluation of one's characteristics and employees (Muhammad Umair Akram, Muhammad Hashim, 2015), it relates to the extent to which an employee feels a high degree of positive affection towards his or her work (Locke, 1969).

In the literature, job satisfaction has been associated with various variables among them organizational justice, and there is a significant and positive relationship between them (Lotfi & Pour, 2013; Ozel & Cahit, 2017). By way of explanation, when employees perceive justice and fair treatment in every aspect in the organization, they are more likely to express higher levels of job satisfaction (Colquitt, 2001), which would consequently improve the individual's productivity, increase commitment degree, reinforce team spirit, and ensure person's physical and mental. Therefore, employees would develop their capacities and competences to learn new job skills rapidly.

4.4 Job Performance:

According to Yean and Yusof (2016, p. 802), "*Job performance refers to job output determined in terms of quantity or quality expected by a superior.* Organ (1988) described job performance as a set of formal job responsibilities that are prescribed by the organization to be evaluated during annual performance appraisals (Russell Cropanzano et al., 2007), in order to regularly monitor and compare initial expectations with the present job progressions, to identify employees' strengths and failures for suggesting improvement areas. It represents the individual's work accomplishment of exerted effort. Rotundo and Sackett (2002) explained that performance is those actions and behaviors that are under the control of the individual and contribute to the goals of the organization.

Improving or deteriorating job performance is dependent on an employee's perception of justice or injustice, according to (Adams, 1965). In this way, numerous studies have stressed that job performance is related positively and meaningfully to organizational justice (Moazzezi et al., 2014; Zgoulli, Abdelaziz Swalhi Saloua, 2017).

Indeed, Organizational justice is a prominent factor that pushes employees to work efficiently. Moazzezi et al, (2014) have recommended setting up certain organizational justice practices that affect its dimensions in order to promote employee's job performance, for instance establishing a fair salary and award system, adjusting and dividing employees working volume without discrimination, making sure that all the collected information is complete and clear before job decision-making, presenting enough justification and explanation about the decision-making, respecting employees' rights and duties in decisions making...

4.5 Employees' Organizational Citizenship Behavior:

(Organ, 1988) defined Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as employees' voluntary and willingness to accomplish their duties within the organization and to follow its rules and functioning without necessarily being influenced by certain recognition or a formal reward system. In other words, when employees feel that they are justly treated, they are more likely to perform in doing extra-role behaviors (Katz, 1964) including "*volunteering ideas, self-development, and defending the organization's reputation*" (Russell Cropanzano et al., 2016, p. 4).

Numerous studies have revealed that organizational justice has a robust and positive correlation with organizational citizenship behavior (e.g., Musringudin, Makruf Akbar, 2017; Nowkarizi & Sharif, 2016), Positive impression and judgment towards the organization, motivates individuals to participate actively and to perform more OCB, like making voluntary extra efforts, voicing constructive suggestions and showing support and consideration to

coworkers. Therefore, this can create a good social interaction between employees with a sense of community, improve people's levels of work meaningfulness and develop organizations' effectiveness and performance as a whole.

4.6 Organizational Trust:

Trust is a perishable commodity within any organization (Hoy & Tarter, 2004), it is considered as a cornerstone to attain organizational effectiveness and a competitive advantage for organizations, it refers to *“a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability based upon positive expectations of the intentions or behavior of another”* (Rousseau et al., 1998, p. 395). It is the willingness to accept vulnerability based on positive expectations of an organization.

Maintaining trust in any organization is a mutual and reciprocal duty between managers and employees. Colquitt et al, (2001) concluded that organizational justice predicts trust and there is a significant and positive correlation between these two variables. Likewise, justice in the organization guarantees that employees trust their peers, their supervisors, their organization and the processes in the organization, which improves their motivation to adhere and align themselves with organization values and objectives.

4.7 Employees Health and wellbeing:

In order to achieve the organization's goals, employers pay more attention to the health and wellbeing of their employees, because they have a salient role in improving organizational efficiency (Iqbal & Ahmad, 2016), which is one of the issues considered to be fundamental in organizational management. Plenty of studies in different organizational contexts have corroborate that organizational justice is a determinant of well-being and health. For instance, organizational justice contributes to reduce the risk of productivity loss and sickness absence (Ybema et al., 2016), develops employees' mental health (Ndjaboué et al., 2012), ameliorates the psychological well-being (PW) of employees (Park et al., 2019) and protects against different dangerous diseases such as coronary heart disease (Kivimaki et al., 2006; Ylipaavalniemi et al., 2005). Indeed, fairness is a useful tool to improve employees' health and wellbeing in order to increase organizational productivity and to enhance the quality of working life.

Nevertheless, perceived injustice in the workplace can increase negative physical, physiological and behavioral disease which damages employee's health such as: mental distress, inflammation, stress, sleeping problems, psychiatric disorders, cognitive impairments, cardiovascular disease and the worst impact cardiovascular death (Elovainio et al., 2010; Kivimaki et al., 2006; Kivimäki et al., 2003; Ylipaavalniemi et al., 2005).

4.8 Counterproductive work behavior:

The counterproductive work behavior is a negative and harmful phenomenon that has been spreading in organizations. It has malicious and costly impacts, like negatively affecting organizations performance (Bunk & Magley, 2013).

In the literature, it was discussed various forms of counterproductive work behavior that may occur in the workplace, for example: interpersonal abuse, sabotage, theft, production deviance and withdrawal. In that way (Idiakheua & Obetoh, 2012) added elements constituting the counterproductive work behavior that are: (Al-A'wasa, 2018)

- The intention to harm.
- Having a target of organization or individuals or both.
- Persistence of the act.
- The depth and intensity of the workplace behavior.

Perceived unfairness may increase interpersonal conflicts at the workplace and lead to a heightened propensity to turnover (Daileyl & Kirk, 1992), and steal (Greenberg, 1993), file a grievance (Taylor et al., 1987).

For instance, a longitudinal study was conducted among 700 employed people aged 45–64 years has found that the perception of injustice in the workplace can cause frustration that may evolve into burnout or destructive organizational behaviors, such as theft, sabotage, withdrawal, harassment (Shkoler & Tziner, 2017). Another study was carried out with a random sample that consists of 340 employees, findings showed that there is a negative relationship of moderate strength between the organizational justice dimensions and the counterproductive work behavior (Al-A'wasa, 2018).

5. Proposed theoretical model:

Based on the previous studies' findings of literature review, a research framework has been developed to elaborate a holistic view of organizational justice perception and to scrutinize the relationship between organizational justice dimensions and its significant impacts. This relationship is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Consequences of the perceived organizational justice on behaviors, attitudes and health

Source: Authors

In summary, Adams' (1963) equity theory and Blau's (1964) social exchange theory explain the interactional relationship between perceived organizational justice and the several behavioral, attitudinal and health variables. As indicated above, Adams' equity theory (1963) highlights that the relationship between the employee and the employer is framed by the exchange. These relationships are expressed in terms of the contributions/remuneration's ratio. Contributions refer to the efforts made by an individual, while rewards are the benefits resulting from the efforts made. For instance, an organization expects loyalty, sincerity, and performance from its employees and, on the other hand, the members expect reciprocal fairness in outcomes of their efforts for the organization: they expect to receive outcomes proportionally with contributions made for the organization. Following the analysis of the ratio, the individual compares its results with a referent's, to know whether the allocation of resources is equitable. If the ratio is higher, the worker will use a strategy to reduce his or her contributions (Adams, 1965), which will be logically accompanied by negative attitudinal and behavioral reactions (e.g. low commitment, low performance, low trust, low productivity, lack of voluntary tasks, high levels of turnover). Broadly, employees become demotivated to adhere to the organization's values and objectives. In that sense, in reference to the Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), that bases on the norm of reciprocity, people act in accordance with what they perceive and receive, when they feel surrounded by a fair organizational system, they believe that they are obliged to make a quid pro quo with positive behaviors, and they are more likely to engage in activities that enhance the organizational environment (e.g. organizational identification (Ashforth & Mael, 1989), organizational citizenship behaviors (Organ, 1988); job performance (Rotundo, 2002), organizational commitment (Steers, 1977). However, negative justice perceptions lead systematically to destructive organizational behaviors and counterproductive organizational behaviors, because they have the intention to harm their colleagues or their organization with aggressive behaviors as a counterpart of injustice (Spector et al. 2006).

6. Conclusion:

The aim of this paper was to portray a holistic overview of the perceived organizational justice and to determine its major outcomes. Therefore, giving importance to organizational justice perceptions in the organizational business should be a priority, it helps decision makers to understand and analyze the relevant impacts of the individual's evaluation and perception of fairness, in order to predict and well manage the likely attitudinal, behavioral and counterproductive reactions.

Justice judgment is a two-sided coin. On the negative side, "*injustice*" is related to the emergence of negative emotions, with the intensification of work stress and with a greater motivation to engage in such counterproductive behaviors towards the organization or its members such as interpersonal conflicts, sabotage, steal, theft, production deviance and withdrawal. Besides, when the employee perceives injustice in the workplace, physical, physiological and psychological diseases can be triggered which can damage his health. Consequently, this may engender increased absenteeism and turnover, low productivity and affect negativity the organizational performance and success. In short, neither employee nor organization wins; both are losers.

On the positive side, "*justice*" can do much more than prevent these unfortunate consequences. In other words, studies have corroborated that when employees perceive equal distribution of outcomes, participatory and fair decision-making processes, dignified and respectful treatments and clear explanation of information. Reciprocally, they tend to express their attachment, belongingness, commitment, identification, satisfaction and trust toward their firm with an increased sense of pride, esteem and psychological well-being, because, they align themselves with organizational values and objectives, attempting to improve their job

performance, adopting extra role behaviors like voicing constructive suggestions and helping coworkers, in addition to defending the organization's reputation as a whole. Hence, organizational justice is a sound strategic investment, it creates powerful benefits for organizations and employees alike and goes beyond acting fairly and doing the right thing, to ensure competitive advantage climate and organizational success.

Indeed, several scholars have focused their gaze on analyzing the organizational justice perceptions at the individual level. For future contributions, it will be interesting to scrutinize the unit or collective level of justice perception (Justice climate, justice climate strength, and peer justice) (R. S. Cropanzano et al., 2015), in the objective of understanding shared fairness evaluations within organizational groups. In addition, organizational justice is studied with many independent variables in the literature that have known a scant attention and that we highly recommend to be researched in further works, it is about antecedents and factors that would derive employees to shape perceptions of organizational justice in the workplace. To this end, a thorough analysis of this issue will provide the scientific research community and managers with a clear insight of how and why fairness judgments are made.

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